

DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION COMPETENCE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE BASED ON ANIMATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The article is about issues related to the process of teaching English oral speech to elementary school students, and its subject is "oral speech skills", they start high school Inner classes form the methodological basis of the formation system in English language education. English language especially for students from primary school to increase interest in learning, one of the most important elements in learning a foreign language is the formation of vocabulary and strengthening of learned words by combining learned words and forming simple sentences, using visual aids, memorizing words belonging to the same group, colors, days of the week, months, seasons and similar words in the form of poetry leaves a deep impression on the child's mind.

Introduction:

It is known that oral speech is the process of listening and understanding and speaking listening comprehension belongs to the receptive-informational type of speech activity. Without this type of speech activity, communication through the medium of language does not take place. In addition, the process of teaching the language is also carried out by the auditory method. By this, syllables, words, phrases, and sentences are formed in the minds of students. In this process, listening comprehension is an effective way to remember language material serves.

Teaching listening comprehension is one of the main tasks in the primary grades of secondary general education schools. A person usually achieves spiritual maturity through the activities of seeing, hearing (listening), and reading. In psycholinguistics, listening comprehension is defined as the process of decoding information coming through the sound channel. "Listening comprehension is a three-stage activity, behind general auditory perception (acoustic apperception), phonemic differentiation of the sound side of words and understanding of their essence, the content of the speech is perceived, learned and, finally, understood" [1].

When listening and understanding speech in the native language, the form and content are perceived as a whole, while in English, the combination of the means of expression (language material) and the expressed content (text) is somewhat difficult. To improve the

content, students need to master the lexical, grammatical, and pronunciation skills of the language. Knowledge of lexis and pronunciation in understanding the text is of particular importance in understanding the general content, and mastering grammar in understanding the content with specific details.

In short, listening comprehension means hearing or understanding the speaker's speech directly or with the help of technical means. In other words, listening comprehension means perceiving the speech of others (live or mechanically recorded) and understanding its content. In listening comprehension, the teacher's speech, audio-technical tools - tape recording, radio broadcasting, sound slide film, movie (video) film or its fragment, and television programs serve as the main sources of information acquisition through the auditory sense and analyzer. In secondary schools, the teacher, audiocassettes, radio broadcasts, sound slides, or English speech in movies and TV shows serve as a source for listening comprehension. Audiotext is understood after listening once. When listening two or more times, a new educational task is given in each case. For example, (1) Listen and answer the questions; (2) Listen and give attention to ...; (3) Listen and find ... etc.

Listening comprehension, as one of the main types of speech activity, is taught in the manner of goals and means applied to the secondary school environment: (1) acquisition of oral communication, that is, speaking and listening comprehension at the same time, interlocutors take turns speaking and listening perform comprehension actions; (2) listening comprehension is acquired as a special type of communicative activity, in other words, the information (information) in the speech heard in the style of an oral story, a movie is assimilated.

The success of listening comprehension depends on several factors, the most important of which are individual age characteristics of the listener, speed of perception, and conditions (speed, amount and size of information, supports of perception). Listening comprehension is closely related to reading and speaking types of speech activity. Because of this, the types of speech activity have similarities and differences. These are the following: Reading, listening, and reading are receptive types of speech activity because they are aimed at receiving information. This type of speech activity is precognition and assumption.

In conclusion, Teaching English in general educational institutions should be aimed not only at mastering the program material but also at identifying gifted children and organizing additional work with them [2]. language teaching to young children should be conducted as an interesting activity, not as a duty, and using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. The importance of learning foreign languages should be properly explained to children through natural conditions.

References:

1. Жалолов Ж. Чет тил ўқитиш методикаси. –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1996. –368 б.
2. Khurshedovna K. M., Akramovna A. Z. Teaching English Activities for the Gifted And Talented Students //Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 374-375.